

The Mediating role of Information Technology Capability on Relationship Between Technology Intelligence And Performance of Selected Manufacturing Firms in FCT-Abuja, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the mediating role of technology capability on the relationship between technology intelligence and performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT-Abuja, Nigeria. This study adopted a survey research design. The population of this study comprised of 155 employees of 31 selected manufacturing firms in FCT-Abuja, Nigeria. The sample size used was same as population of the study and convenient sampling technique was used to select the respondents. The study utilized questionnaire as the instrument for data collection. The data collected for the study was analyzed using Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) in determining the measurement, structural models and hypotheses testing through SmartPLS 3.0 software. The study found that technology identification, technology evaluation and technology capability has positive and significant effect on performance; while technology acquisition has positive and insignificant effect on performance; and technology application have negative but insignificant effect on the performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT-Abuja. The study also found that technology capability mediate the relationship between technology acquisition, technology evaluation and performance; while technology capability does not mediate the relationship between technology identification, technology application and performance. Base on the findings, the study concludes that technology capability partially mediate the relationship between technology intelligence and performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT-Abuja, Nigeria. The study thus recommended among others, that selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria should change from their current technology application and adopt regular monitoring and maintenance at each face of technology implementation so as to meet up with the purpose of such technology in order to improve their overall performance.

Key words: Technology Intelligence, Technology Identification, Technology acquisition, Technology evaluation, Technology application, Technology Capability, Performance.

Introduction

Globally, continuous improvement in overall performance is the major concern of every manufacturing firm because of the diverse competition in the industry. In developed nations like Japan, China, Germany and United State of America, manufacturing industry keep booming and contribute largely to their economy. In Africa particularly Nigeria with abundant natural resources, it is expected that manufacturing sector should be the larger contributor to the economic growth, but the situation is different as performance of the majority manufacturing sector is poor and therefore contributing less to the economic growth. Performance is critical for every firm, as it enhances shareholder's value and capability to generate earnings from invested capital. Therefore, the performance of manufacturing firms has become a great concern to managers and all other stake holders as the business environment becomes more competitive and dynamic.

Firm's performance refers to the ways by which they achieve their organizational set goals. It is the ability of an organization to achieve the expected results and attain its set goals by effectively utilizing its available resources (Chang, & Chuang, 2016; Matin & Sabagh, 2015). This implies that for every firm to gain or attain high performance level, such firm must have capability to contend with the ever increasing competitive and dynamic business environment, and this can be achieved through technology intelligence.

Technology intelligence is therefore referring to activities that create an essential and timely insight into technological trends and facts (threats and opportunities) outside an organization by collecting, analyzing, and disseminating relevant and appropriate information, and thus support decision-making and planning processes related to technological issues as well as corporate management (Ranjbar & Cho, 2016). According to Ranjbar and Cho, (2016) technology intelligence, consists of some direct activities such as identifying information needs, collecting, analyzing, disseminating, and applying properly relevant technological information, which would eventually lead to value creation for an organization through an improved decision-making process.

The fundamental aim of manufacturing firms adopting technology intelligence is to identify, acquire, evaluate and apply or implement latest technologies to cover for the ever changing technological challenges with the hope to improve the overall level of performance of their enterprises, yet the level performance of most of manufacturing firms in Nigeria is still low as majority of them struggle to get the latest technologies in place. This gave raised to this study's mind set to investigate effectiveness of the moderating role of

technology capability on the relationship between technology intelligence and performance of the selected manufacturing firms FCT Abuja, Nigeria.

In furtherance, while there have been a number of research in this area (e.g. Kilic, et al. 2016; Donat, 2017; Manzini & Nasullaev, 2017; Ezuma et al., 2019; Mallinguh, et al., 2020) there appears to be paucity of empirical research studies on the moderating role of technology capability on the relationship between technology intelligence and performance of manufacturing firms in developing nations like Nigeria. Hence, based on the above problem and identified gap, the objective of this study is to examine the moderating role of technology capability on the relationship between technology intelligence (proxy by technology identification, technology acquisition, technology evaluation and technology application) on the performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria. In order to achieve the above objective, the study hypothesises as follows:

H_{01a}: technology identification has no significant effect on performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria.

H_{01b}: technology capability does not mediate the relationship between technology identification and performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria.

H_{02a}: technology acquisition has no significant effect on performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria.

H_{02b}: technology capability does not mediate the relationship between technology acquisition and performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria.

H_{03a}: technology evaluation has no significant effect on performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria.

H_{03b}: technology capability does not mediate the relationship between technology evaluation and performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria.

H_{04a}: technology application has no significant effect on performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria.

H_{04b}: technology capability does not mediate the relationship between technology application and performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria.

H₀₅: technology capability has no significant effect on performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria.

Literature Review

Concept of Technology Intelligence

Technology intelligence is a set of activities that enable a company to monitor technological advances that affect its products, raw materials, processes, and markets, as well as examine its environment in order to capitalize on potential advantages during technological

changes (threats or opportunities) (Arman & Foden, 2010). Similarly, Gonçalves and de Almeida (2019) defined technology intelligence as activities that support decision-making of technological and general management concerns by taking advantages of a well-timed preparation of relevant information on technological facts and trends (opportunities and threats) of the organization's environment by means of collection, analysis, and dissemination. Also, Asikhia et al. (2019) defined technology intelligence as information sensitive to firm about the development of external sciences and technology that can affect the company's competitive position. They further stated that adopting technology intelligence is nothing more than an informal technology monitoring and is also a structured process that involves four major steps: firstly, planning, organizing and conducting competitive intelligence efforts, secondly, intelligent information gathering, thirdly, analysis of data and lastly, dissemination of results for practical uses.

Technology intelligence permits firms to respond to threats from, as well as to identify and exploit opportunities resulting from technological and scientific changes. It is usually focused on technological trends and scientific breakthroughs and can develop information on opportunities as well as threats for the firm. Technology intelligence supports innovation strategies as well as research and development, and has become a growth area that grants firms competitive edge (Santo & Correia, 2010). Other advantages of technology intelligence include better communication, easy access to information, Social networking, efficiency and productivity, improved decision making and encourages innovation and (Majidfar & Salami, 2011).

According to Kilic, et al. (2016), technology intelligence (TI) encompasses the activities related to the collection, analysis and communication of relevant information on technological trends to support technological and more general decisions of the company. They see TI as the capture or acquisition and delivery of technological information as part of the process whereby a company develops an awareness of technological threats and opportunities. They further states that TI involves four processes namely, technology ignition/identification, technology acquisition, technology evaluation and technology application. The goal of technology intelligence is to exploit potential opportunities and to defend against potential threats, through prompt delivery of relevant information about technological trends in the environment of the company in order to stay competitive (Kilic, et al., 2016). This study therefore adopts the process of technology intelligence suggested by Kilic, et al. (2016).

Technology Identification

Technology identification consists of initiation of the needs of technology information compliant with the objectives of the organization. Identification can be done through the information from external and internal environment of the organization such as the customers, the experts in the organization or even with the evolution of the products and environment. Identification of the need is followed by the identification of the sources for the data to be watched. Tasks and data sources are relocated through the plans and work breakdown structures (Veugelers et al., 2010). Ranjbar and Cho (2016) propose a distinction between inside-out and outside-in viewpoints for assessing technological information needs. The first focuses on technology observation within the present activity area. The latter is a non-biased assessment of technology trends in general. In most situations, technology planning activities, such as technology road mapping and scenario analysis, include technological and market factors and are cross-functionally coordinated. New important challenges, such as upcoming technology or competitors, are found as a result of this process. Also mentioned are the primary drivers of industry development and product functioning from the customer's perspective (Ranjbar & Cho, 2016).

Technology Acquisition

Technology acquisition, this has to do with acquisition of information regarding the identified technology, searching for data and storing it in a form that may be retrieved when needed and accessible within the organization. Information is distilled through the objectives defined in previous step. Information sources should be scanned and watched periodically mostly on scientific publications, standards, customer, and supplier feedback. Related information sources can be defined as periodical magazines, books, patents, standard documentaries, forums, societies etc. Informal sources such as fairs, congress, customer audits, supplier quotations, product briefings are also watched (Bucher et al., 2003).

The goal of technology information gathering is to obtain the necessary information based on a projected information need. A data collection form, comprising the type and number of personnel collecting data, as well as appropriate information sources that provide access to the sought-after data, must be selected (Ranjbar & Cho, 2016). This is usually accomplished through two types of information sources: formal and informal. Research programs, papers, patents, conference proceedings, online databases, journals, newsletters, and the internet are all formal sources of knowledge. Regular meetings, memberships, site visits, phone calls, unintentional contact, small talk, interview, and expert panels with some actors such as competitors, clients, suppliers, start-up companies,

university professors, professional societies, conferences, and alliance partners are also informal sources of information (Lee & Yoon, 2015).

Technology Evaluation

Technology evaluation, this has to do with the evaluation of information generated by extrapolative, explorative or normative ways. Methods such as publication frequency analysis, publication citation analyses, quantitative conference analyses, patent frequency analyses, S-curve analyses, benchmarking, portfolio analyses, roadmap analyses, experience curve analyses, Delphi studies, expert panels, flexible expert interviews, lead user analyses and quality function deployment etc. are used to evaluate technology required (Lichtenthaler, 2005). The objective of the information evaluation is to analyze the importance of the gathered information in order to arrive at the needed technology. Filter, integration, and assessment of information are the three functions of evaluation. The purpose of the filter function is to limit the amount of information by determining its relevance to the firm and assessing its quality. The integration function is responsible for integrating information in the context of the firm, which necessitates the acquisition of relevant prior knowledge. The assessment function then determines the strategic significance of data for the company. At this point, information transforms into intelligence (Manzini & Nasullaev, 2017).

Technology Application

Technology application describes the analysis and implementation of technological intelligence. The analysis on the information should be put together in the reports in order to be included in the decision making process. The key factors that will be considered in the relevance of the information will be; awareness, risk reduction, required developments, innovation and cooperation and fit with the organization objectives. Not only will the information be treated individually, but also synergy between different areas of knowledge should be explored. A close look will be held to check signs and factors that can impact the organization (Pena, 2009).

IT Capability

Halac (2015) defined technical capability as a set of functional abilities that are reflected in the firm's performance through various technological activities and whose ultimate goal is to generate difficult-to-copy organizational abilities in order to manage firm level value. Because specific technology resource combinations give hard to copy and unique positions, technology resources are at the center of competitive advantage. The efficiency with which those resource combinations of capability have been packed determines the

technological capability's strength (Voudouris, et al., 2012).

Technology capability describes a firm's ability to assemble and deploy IT-based resources in combination with other firms' resources (Bharadwaj, 2000). Some scholars have argued that IT capability is more than just an ability that a firm possesses, but rather a complex package of IT-related resources, skills and knowledge that enable firms to coordinate activities and other resources to produce desired results (Stoel & Muhanna, 2009). Firms with the ability to plan and integrate their IT resources are more positioned to capture information about customers, share knowledge and improve business processes (Karimi et al., 2001; Mithas et al., 2011). To attain superior performance from IT resources, the resource-based view of IT advocates that firms need to create a firm-wide IT capability by combining IT infrastructure, human IT skills, and IT-enabled intangibles with other firm-specific resources (Wade & Hulland, 2004).

Lall (1992) views information technological capability as a continuous process of interacting with the environment to create, accumulate, and absorb technological knowledge and skills required by the firm. According to Kumar, et al. (2004), a firm achieves technological capability through process learning. The ability to create and manage changes in technologies in production is necessary if a firm has to achieve success in terms of superior performance (Bell & Pavitt, 1995; Trez,et al., 2012; Zawislak, et al., 2012).

Performance

There is no generally accepted definition and measurement for performance. Each definition comes from a specific perspective and is based on the context and features of a firm performance system (Yıldız et al. 2012). Kakhki and Palvia (2016) define performance as the set of metrics used to quantify both the efficiency and effectiveness of actions. According to Ezuma et al. (2019), performance can be conceptualized as the level at which the firm effectively meets its planned objectives through efficient utilization of its fewest available resources, together with the development of its capacity to meet future opportunities and challenges to satisfy the stakeholder needs, as well as innovation of quality products. Performance is thus an important concern of organizations because it reflects the extent to which their mission, vision and goal statements are achieved (Ogunyomi & Bruning, 2015). The success of all enterprises, whether small or medium or large enterprises can be seen through their performance. According to Samat, et al. (2019), enterprises performs can be defined by their capability to lead in creating employment, wealth creation business survival and sustainability.

Yıldız et al. (2012) identify profitability, sale growth, market share, new product launch, return on sale (ROS), return on investment (ROI) and customer satisfaction as the most important quantitative criteria for firm performance. While, Kihara, et al. (2016) identify Total Profits, volume of sales, number of employees, geographical market size, returns from assets invested (ROA), returns from borrowed money (ROE), number of customers, size of organization, quality service/product and internal work processes as performance measurement.

Empirical Review

Technology Identification and Performance

Waithaka, et al. (2016) examined technology oriented competitive intelligence practice proxy by technology identification and firms performance in Nairobi, Kenya. The study adopted a mixed design of descriptive and explanatory survey research. The study used firms listed on the Nairobi Securities Exchange. The target population for the study was all the sixty firms listed on the Nairobi Securities Exchange (NSE). The study targeted the manager or director in-charge of planning /strategy in each firm as the unit for observation. The study used primary data which was collected by the use of a semi-structured questionnaire and secondary data was obtained from published financial reports. The data collected was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics tools such as correlation and regression analysis. The study found that technology identification has a positive and statistically significant relationship with the performance in firms listed on the Nairobi Securities Exchange. The study failed to explain whether it's used the entire population as the sample size or failed to determine the sample size. In addition the study used both primary and secondary data which is not appropriate for the data analysis and therefore limits the reliability of the findings from the study. Also, the study was done in Nairobi, Kenya and focused on the firms listed on the Nairobi Securities Exchange but failed to differentiate the type of the firm its concentrated on.

Technology Acquisition and Performance

Mallinguh, et al. (2020) examined the effect of technology acquisition on SMEs performance; the role of innovation, export and the perception of owner-managers. The study focused on the effect of a capital budget's proportion for acquiring new technology and sale performance between 2017–2019. The study adopted a survey research design. The population of the study comprised of SMEs owner-managers and used sample of 101 Kenyan SMEs. The study utilize questionnaires as the instrument for data collection. The data collected for the study was analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation matrix and ordinary least square regression. The study found that technology acquisition has

positive and significant effect on SMEs performance. it also found that the proportion of the capital budget allocated for the acquisition of technology positively and significantly influences sales. The study therefore conclude that

Kilic, et al. (2016) examined the technology intelligence process in scope of Turkish technopark firms. The study adopted a survey research design. The study covered 13 technoparks in Turkey. The empirical data was obtained from 136 technopark firms and evaluated by the context of TI model synthesized by the study based on the literature. The study utilized questionnaire as the instrument for data collection. The data collected for the study was analyzed using descriptive statistics of simple percent and charts with the aid of SPSS. The study found that TI mechanisms of the technopark firms are unstructured and technopark firm's do not allocate enough resources for acquisition of TI, they use the environments that can be easily reached such as internet and periodical magazines, and analyze the data about technology by using heuristic methods mostly

Technology Evaluation and Performance

Donat (2017) investigated the impact of technology intelligence on the business strategy performance relationship in building core competence in Uganda small medium enterprises (SME's). The study examined the moderating effect of technology intelligence on the relationship between business strategy and performance of SMEs in the Uganda's manufacturing sector. The study adopted qualitative methods. The study relied on previous research. The study found that technological intelligence has a significant impact on business strategy performance. The findings of the study also indicated that the performance of SME vary with the choice of the business strategies they adopted that result to building core competences with regard to the competitive advantages. Additionally, to a certain degree, the findings of the study suggest technology intelligence as measured by technological complexity of process moderates the relationship between business strategy and the performance of SME's. The study only relied on previous studies and did not conduct any statistical analysis, therefore limited the relevancy and the generalization of the findings.

Technology Application and Performance

Ezuma et al. (2019) examined whether network competence matters in the relationship between technology usage and organizational performance of medium-sized manufacturing enterprises in the state of Lagos, Nigeria. The study adopted survey research design. The population used in the study comprised of the total 619 registered medium-sized manufacturing enterprises in Lagos. The data for the study were based on the responses to structured questionnaires that were completed by 245 owners/managers of medium sized manufacturing enterprises in Lagos, Nigeria. Descriptive analysis (mean

values, frequencies and percentages), and Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) using AMOS was employed for inferential statistics to analyzed the data gathered and test the hypothesis. The findings from the study showed that the integration of network competence practices and technology intelligence usage did translate to improved organizational performance. Network competence served to promote a degree of trust within and outside interdependent firms. The findings of the study also indicated that network competence partially mediated the relationship between technology intelligence usage and organizational performance of medium-sized manufacturing enterprises. The study focused only on registered medium-sized manufacturing enterprises in the state of Lagos, Nigeria, as such the findings from the study cannot be generalized to other states in Nigeria.

Manzini and Nasullaev (2017) examined technology intelligence practice toward firms performance, a systematic literature review of empirical studies and agenda for further research. The study presented a systematic literature review of empirical studies on Technology intelligence with an objective to identify main characteristics and trends of the literature on the implementation of Technology intelligence toward firm's performance. To achieve this objective the study reviewed 138 documents systematically (following a scientifically robust methodology) in terms of research methodology, research context and content. Citation network analysis was adopted to generate thematic clusters. The presented investigation provides (i) an overview of the methodologies used in literature and the types of empirical studies (case studies, surveys, evolution investigations, interviews, experiments, etc.) as well as the related diffusion; (ii) a summary of the research content (topics, thematic areas) in the practice of Technology intelligence; (iii) a picture of the various contexts and levels in which the practice of Technology intelligence has been studied (industries, sectors, technologies, countries). The study found that knowledge on implementation process of TI toward firm's performance is still yet to rich it's potential. The study relied only on empirical studies and did not conduct any statistical analysis, therefore there is a huge demand for contributions which will aims to conduct empirical studies on TI and use statistical tools for data analysis.

Technology Capability and Performance

Mochoge, et al. (2020) the study determined the effect of technological capability and firm performance among commercial banks in Kenya. Explanatory research design was used in the study. The population used for the study comprised of 25 banks within Nairobi CBD. From the 25 banks database, there is a total of 225 heads of departments. Using this Nassiuma (2000) formula a sample of 119 head of departments was selected using stratified

random sample was used. The study utilized a questionnaire to gather the data used. Cronbach alpha coefficient test was employed to measure the internal consistency of the instruments. The study used descriptive statistics such as means, standard deviation, frequency and percentages. Multiple linear regression analysis was used to test the hypothesis. The study found that technological operating capability, technological upgrading capability and technological acquiring capability had positive and significant effects on bank performance.

Kabiru, et al. (2015) examined the relationship between information technology capability and organizational performance in Nigerian banks. The study adopted a survey research design. The study used stratified random sampling and simple random probability procedure in selecting the organizations as the sample. The sample size used for the study comprised 560 bank employees. The study used questionnaires as the instrument for data collection. Multiple regression analysis was used to analyze the data collected using SPSS software. The study found that IT capability is significantly related to organization performance of banks based on resource based view(RBV) of organization performance. The study used cross sectional design for survey research that captures the perceptions of respondents at a point in time. Thus, the study cannot prove causal relationships on a longitudinal basis.

Theoretical Framework

The underpinning theory for this study is dynamic capabilities theory which was propounded by Teece et al.(1997). The ability of a company to integrate, build, and reconfigure internal and external capabilities in response to a quickly changing environment is known as dynamic capability. Dynamic capabilities develop from the firm's assets, evolutionary path, and managerial routines (Teece et al. 1997; Barney, 2001; Zello & Winter 2002). Dynamic capability consists of organizational and managerial processes with three roles: coordination /integration; learning; and reconfiguration (Teece et al., 1997). In this perspective, the ability of a company to identify, acquire, evaluate and apply or implement the appropriate technology intelligence will aid the company to be up-to-day technological therefore serve as a competitive advantage for such firm within the industry.

Research Methodology

This study examined examines the moderating role of technology capability on the relationship between technology intelligence (proxy by technology identification, technology acquisition, technology evaluation and technology application) on the

performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria. This study adopted a survey research design. According to Olawale (2022), there are 95 registered Manufacturing Companies in Abuja as at January 20, 2022. However, this study covered only 31 registered Manufacturing Companies in Abuja and randomly selected 5 senior staff of each selected firm. Therefore, the population of this study comprised of 155 staff from the selected firms. The justification for choosing this location was based on the fact that FCT-Abuja being the Capital of Nigeria attracts concentration of manufacturing firms. Also the justification for choosing senior staff was based on the fact that they are in best position to respond to issues relating to the variables used in this study. Since the population for this study is not too large, the sample size used was same as the population and convenience sampling technique was used to select the respondents for the study.

The study utilized questionnaire as the instrument for data collection, the questionnaire was adapted from the work of Kilic, et al. (2016), Halac (2015), Kihara, et al. (2016). The independents variables are technology identification (8 items), technology acquisition (8 items), technology evaluation (8 items) & technology application (8 items) a adapted from the work of Kilic, et al. (2016). The dependent variable (performance) questionnaire was adapted from the work of Kihara, et al. (2016) with 5 items. The mediator variable (technology capability (10 items) questionnaire was adapted from the work of Halac (2015). The reliability of the instrument used was accessed using Cronbach alpha. Cronbach alpha value of greater than 0.7 is appropriate (Hair, et al., 2014). Out of one hundred and fifty-five (155) copies of questionnaire administered, ninety seven (97) copies which constituted 62% of total questionnaire administered were valid for the analysis. The data was analyzed using Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) in determining the measurement, structural models and hypotheses testing through SmartPLS 3.0 software (Hair, et al., 2016). Validity and reliability of the measures were first of all ascertained before testing the hypothesized relationships using algorism and bootstrapping techniques (Hair, et al., 2014). The model for the PLS-SEM is depicted pictorially below:

Fig. 1: Model Specification

Measurement of Variables

Performance (dependent variable), proxy by increase in market shares, increase in annual profit, increase in sales, access to further markets and increase in output. Adopted from Kihara, et al. (2016).

Technology intelligence (independent variable), proxy by technology identification, technology acquisition, technology evaluation and technology application.

Technology identification was measured by Participating in technical societies, industrial platforms, Participating in technical seminars, conferences, fairs etc. Networking with young firms, Monitoring industrial and related standards, Monitoring industrial and technology websites, Participation in supplier workshops and Monitoring national and international patent databases. Adapted from Kilic, et al. (2016).

Technology acquisition was measured by provisions are made to buy new technology, new technology is purchased to satisfy the customer's new requirements, new technology is purchase based on management recommendation, new technology is purchase to decrease the design and production costs, new technology is purchase to meet up with new commercial and technological opportunities, new technology is purchase to take advantage of the capabilities and resources of other institutions/companies. Adapted from Kilic, et al. (2016),

Technology evaluation measurement items are: Patent analysis is held concerning technology need, Bibliometric analysis is held concerning technology, Technology trend analysis is held based on technology need, Roadmap analyses are held based on technology required, Benchmarking processes are held based on technology need, Technology development analysis is held on technology need, Quality Function Deployment analysis is held concerning, creative problem solving methods of technology need are done depending on employee experience. Adapted from Kilic, et al. (2016),

Technology application measurement items are: Technology are put to used base on recommendation from top management, used of the new technology are discussed on daily basis, use of the new technology are shared within whole organization, Technology is put to use only on required unit, Technology used are shared with the project or business partners, Technology used are integrated to R&D, Technology used are integrated to new product development process and new technology are input for strategic goals development process. Adapted from Kilic, et al. (2016),

Technology capability (Mediator variable). The measuring items are:

Our firm is one of the leaders in our industry to establish technology standards.

Our firm is one of the leaders in our industry to upgrade technology standards.

Our firm has a competitive and powerful technology strategy.

Our firm has strong technological skills in various fields.

Our firm leads technological innovation in our industry.

Our firm is skillful in applying new technologies to problem solving.

Our firm has the ability to accurately predict future technological trends.

Our firm is qualified to attract and motivate talented experts.

Our firm monitors up-to-date technological changes and developments closely.

Our firm improves technical skills of employees by frequently held training programs.

Adapted from Halac (2015).

Results and Discussion

Measurement Model Evaluation

The measurement model was evaluated using convergent validity. Convergent validity is determined by examining the factor loadings, composite reliability and average variance extracted (AVE) (Gholami, et al, 2013). The constructs used in this study has achieved the acceptable loadings of above 0.6; composite reliability (CR) of the constructs used were all above 0.7, although some of the constructs were dropped due to low loadings as shown in the fig. 2 below, and Average variance extracted (AVE) were all above 0.5 as recommended by Hair et al. (2014). The above is shown in the fig. 2 and the table 1 below.

Fig. 2: Measurement model of the study constructs and indicators.

Table 1**Convergent validity**

Variables	Indicators	Loadings	Cronbach's		Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
			alpha	rho_A		
Technology Identification	TID1	0.887	0.953	0.961	0.961	0.753
	TID2	0.896				
	TID3	0.863				
	TID4	0.833				
	TID5	0.882				
	TID6	0.885				
	TID7	0.860				
	TID8	0.831				
Technology Acquisition	TAC2	0.715	0.888	0.900	0.915	0.645
	TAC3	0.876				
	TAC4	0.871				
	TAC6	0.704				
	TAC7	0.755				
	TAC8	0.875				
Technology Evaluation	TEV2	0.908	0.967	0.970	0.973	0.836
	TEV3	0.918				
	TEV4	0.947				
	TEV5	0.939				
	TEV6	0.914				
	TEV7	0.893				
	TEV8	0.878				
	Technology Application	TAP1				
TAP2		0.944				
TAP4		0.911				
TAP6		0.939				

	TAP7	0.925				
Technology Capability	TEC1	0.925	0.959	0.960	0.968	0.859
	TEC2	0.944				
	TEC3	0.900				
	TEC5	0.926				
	TEC7	0.940				
Performance	PFM1	0.781	0.872	0.874	0.908	0.664
	PFM2	0.814				
	PFM3	0.732				
	PFM4	0.872				
	PFM5	0.867				

Source: SmartPLS Output, 2022

Table 2 Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

	Performance	Technology Acquisition	Technology Capability	Technology Evaluation	Technology Identification	Technology Application
Performance						
Technology Acquisition	0.384					
Technology Capability	0.137	0.135				
Technology Evaluation	0.367	0.379	0.131			
Technology Identification	0.474	0.483	0.053	0.382		
Technology Application	0.198	0.218	0.131	0.527	0.286	

Source: SmartPLS Output, 2022

The Table 2 shows the results of Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) ratio for the variables used in this research. From the table, the result in all the respective cases show that values are less than 0.9, this therefore indicates that there is absent of discriminate validity problems. That is, the result revealed that there is no problem of discriminate validity in all respective cases as suggested by Henseler, et al. (2015). Discriminate validity problems are present when HTMT values are higher than 0.90 for structural models (Henseler, et al., 2015).

Table 3: Model Goodness of Fit (GoF)

	Saturated	Estimated
	Model	Model
SRMR	0.060	0.060
d_ULS	2.412	2.412
d_G	15.767	15.767
Chi-Square	11,297.402	11,297.402
NFI	0.470	0.470

Source: SmartPLS Output, 2022

The Table 3 shows the result of model goodness of fit. Sequel to the need to validate the PLS model, there is a need to assess the goodness of fit of the model as suggested Hair, et al., (2017). This study used the standardised root mean square residual's (SRMR). The choice of this index was based on the fact that the SRMR provides the absolute fit measure where a value of zero indicates a perfect fit. The study adopted Hu and Bentler (1998) suggestion that a value of less than 0.08 represents a good fit while applying SRMR for model goodness of fit. This study result indicates an SRMR value of 0.060 which is less than 0.08, therefore indicated the fitness of the model as suggested by Hu and Bentler (1998).

Structural Model and Hypotheses Testing

Fig. 4.2: Structural Model and Hypotheses Testing

Table 4: Results of the Structural Model Analysis (Hypotheses Testing)

Hypotheses	Relationship	Path				Decision
		Coefficient	Standard Error	T Statistics	P value	
	Technology Identification ->					
HO1a	Performance	0.321	0.066	4.775	0.000	Rejected
	Technology Identification ->					
HO1b	Technology Capability	0.045	0.067	0.667	0.505	Accepted
	Technology Acquisition ->					
HO2a	Performance	0.126	0.066	1.904	0.057	Accepted

	Technology Acquisition ->					
HO2b	Technology Capability	0.191	0.057	3.242	0.001	Rejected
	Technology Evaluation ->					
HO3a	Performance	0.198	0.072	2.766	0.006	Rejected
	Technology Evaluation ->					
HO3b	Technology Capability	0.161	0.059	2.733	0.006	Rejected
	Technology Application ->					
HO4a	Performance	-0.010	0.061	0.185	0.854	Accepted
	Technology Application ->					
HO4b	Technology Capability	-0.099	0.062	1.551	0.121	Accepted
	Technology Capability ->					
HO5	Performance	0.113	0.049	2.271	0.024	Rejected

Source: SmartPLS Output, 2022

The fig. 4.2 and Table 4 depict the structural model and hypotheses testing for this study. The table 4 shows the values for Beta (β), standard Error, T statistics and P Value. The beta value and the corresponding t-values were used in assessing the structural model in this study. This was done through the bootstrapping procedure.

The bootstrapping output from the Smart PLS shows that path coefficient of technology identification and performance (Technology Identification -> Performance) is positive and statistically significant. The result from the analysis indicates that technology identification has positive and significant effect on performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria at 5% significant level with a fair and positive beta (β) value of 0.321 (32%), t-value of 4.775 which is greater than 1.96 and its corresponding p- value of 0.000 (β Value = 0.321, T-Value = 4.775 and P-Value = 0.000). This result has provided the basis for rejection of the null hypothesis (HO1a) which states that technology identification has no significant effect on performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria. This has proved that the relationship between the two variables (technology identification -> performance) is positive and significant at $p < 0.05$ with a fair beta value and t value above 1.96. In addition, the result of technology identification and technology capability show a β Value of 0.045, T-Value of 0.667 and P-Value of 0.505, this indicates that technology capability does not mediate the relationship between technology identification and performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria at 5% level of significant. This has proved the fact for the acceptance of the HO1b which states that technology capability does not mediate the relationship between technology identification

and performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja. See figure 4.2 and table 4 for the above results.

The result of the test of the hypothesis in respect to technology acquisition and performance (technology acquisition -> performance), the bootstrapping result from the Smart PLS reveals that path coefficient of technology acquisition has positive and insignificant effect on performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria at 5% significant level with a weak but positive Path Coefficient beta (β) value of 0.126 (13%), t-value of 1.904 which is less than 1.96 and its corresponding p- value of 0.057 (β Value=0.126, T-Value=1.904 and P-Value=0.057). This result has not provided the basis for rejection of the null hypothesis (HO2a) which states that technology acquisition has no significant effect on performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria; therefore this null HO2a is accepted. This has proved that the relationship between the two variables (technology acquisition -> performance) is positive but insignificant at $p < 0.05$ with a weak beta value and low t value below 1.96. In addition, the result of technology acquisition and technology capability show the β Value of 0.191, T-Value of 3.242 and P-Value of 0.001, this indicates that technology capability mediate the relationship between technology acquisition and performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria at 5% level of significant. This has proved the fact for the rejection of the HO2b. This result is shown in figure 4.2 and table 4 above.

The bootstrapping output from the Smart PLS shows that path coefficient of technology evaluation and performance (technology evaluation->performance) is positive and statistically significant. The result from the analysis indicates that technology evaluation has positive and significant effect on performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria at 5% significant level with a weak and positive beta (β) value of 0.198 (20%), t-value of 2.766 which is greater than 1.96 and its corresponding p- value of 0.006 (β Value = 0.198, T-Value = 2.766 and P-Value = 0.006). This result has provided the basis for rejection of the null hypothesis (HO3a) which states that technology evaluation has no significant effect on performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria. This has proved that the relationship between the two variables (technology evaluation-> performance) is positive and significant at $p < 0.05$ with a weak beta value and t value above 1.96. In addition, the result of technology evaluation and technology capability how the β Value of 0.161, T-Value of 2.733 and P-Value of 0.006 indicates that technology capability mediate the relationship between technology evaluation and performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria at 5% level of significant. This has provided the basis for the rejection of the HO3b. This result is shown in figure 4.2 and table 4 above.

The result of the test of the hypothesis in respect to technology application and performance (technology application -> performance), the bootstrapping result from the Smart PLS reveals that path coefficient of technology application has negative but insignificant effect on performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria at 5% significant level with a weak negative beta (β) value of -0.010 (10%), t-value of 0.185 which is less than 1.96 and its corresponding p- value of 0.854 (β Value = -0.010, T-Value = 0.185 and P-Value = 0.854). This result has not provided the basis for rejection of the null hypothesis (HO4a) which states that technology application has no significant effect on performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria therefore the HO4a is accepted. This has proved that the relationship between the two variables (technology application -> performance) is negative but insignificant at $p < 0.05$ with a negative weak beta value and low t value below 1.96. In addition, the result of technology application and technology capability shows the β Value of -0.099, T-Value of 1.551 and P-Value of 0.121, this indicates that technology capability does not mediate the relationship between technology application and performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria at 5% level of significant. This has provided the basis for the acceptance of the HO4b. This result is shown in figure 4.2 and table 4 above.

The bootstrapping output from the Smart PLS shows that path coefficient of technology capability and performance (technology capability->performance) is positive and statistically significant. The result from the analysis indicates that technology capability has positive and significant effect on performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria at 5% significant level with a weak and positive beta (β) value of 0.113 (13%), t-value of 2.271 which is greater than 1.96 and its corresponding p- value of 0.024 (β Value = 0.113, T-Value = 2.271 and P-Value = 0.024). This result has provided the basis for rejection of the null hypothesis (HO5) which states that technology capability has no significant effect on performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria. This has proved that the relationship between the two variables (technology capability-> performance) is positive and significant at $p < 0.05$ with a weak beta value and t value above 1.96. This result is shown in figure 4.2 and table 4 above.

Table 5: R Square Result

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Performance	0.262	0.250
Technology Capability	0.058	0.045

2022

The Table 5 explains the predictive relevance of the model, R^2 value from the table shows the variance in the dependent variable (performance) as explained by the independent variables (technology identification, technology acquisition, technology evaluation and technology application). The result shows a low R^2 value of 0.262 (26%) accounted by the predictive variables on the criterion variable of the model. That is, the coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.262 indicates that about 26% of variation in performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria can be explained by the combined effects of technology identification, technology acquisition, technology evaluation and technology application. While the remaining 74% variation in performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria can be explained by other factors or variables not included or captured in this study.

Table 6: Collinearity Statistics (Variance Inflation Factor (VIF))

Variables	VIF
Technology Identification	1.347
Technology Acquisition	1.355
Technology Evaluation	1.558
Technology Application	1.375
Technology Capability	1.062

Source: SmartPLS Output, 2022

The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values of 1.347, 1.355, 1.558, 1.375 and 1.062 for all the respective cases from the table above indicated that the explanatory variables are not highly correlated. These, therefore, show absence of multicollinearity among the independent variables since multicollinearity exists only when the VIF Value is greater than 5. The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) was used to evaluate collinearity of the formative indicators. All the VIF values were less than 5 indicate the absence of critical collinearity issues among the indicators of formatively measured constructs (Hair, et al., 2019).

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examined examines the moderating role of technology capability on the relationship between technology intelligence (proxy by technology identification, technology acquisition, technology evaluation and technology application) on the performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria. The study found that technology identification, technology evaluation and technology capability has positive and significant effect on performance; while technology acquisition has positive and insignificant effect on performance; and technology application have negative but insignificant effect on the performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria. The study also found that technology capability mediate the relationship between technology acquisition, technology evaluation and performance; while technology capability does not mediate the relationship between technology identification, technology application and performance. Base on the findings from this study, the study conclude that technology identification, technology evaluation and technology capability positively and significantly influence the performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria. While technology acquisition positively and insignificantly influence the performance; and technology application negatively but insignificantly influence the performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria. This could be because the selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria have the capability to initiate and evaluate the technology intelligence required but does not have the capacity of to acquire and apply the technology intelligence to the fullest. The study also concludes that technology capability can mediate the relationship between technology acquisition, technology evaluation and performance; but technology capability cannot mediate the relationship between technology identification, technology application and performance of selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria.

Based on the findings and conclusion drawn from this study, the study recommends that:

- i. The selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria should width the scope of their technology identification search by always extending their search for such to developed nations in order to be up-to-date and keep improving the overall performance of their firms.
- ii. The selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria should improve on their current method of acquiring technology by way of employing the experts that will focus on obtaining the exactly technology require, as that will minimize waste and save cost.
- iii. The selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria should maintain their technology evolution process and employ on in-depth assessment before recommending it

for implementation so as to continuing improving their overall performance.

iv The selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria should change from their current technology application and adopt regular monitoring and maintenance at each face of technology implementation so as to meet up with the purpose of such technology in order to improve their overall performance.

v. The selected manufacturing firms in FCT Abuja, Nigeria should keep improving on their technology capability by way of focusing on all processes require having an up dated technology in order to improve their overall performance.

REFERENCES

- Arman, H., & Foden, J. (2010). Combining methods in the technology intelligence process: application in an aerospace manufacturing firm. *R&d Management*, 40(2), 181-194.
- Asikhia, O. A., Magaji, N. & Muritala, A. S. (2019). Technological Intelligence and organisational Performance: Moderating Role of Process Innovation. *Open Journal of Economics and Commerce*, 2(1), 25-31.
- Barney, J., B. (2001). Resource-Based Theories of Competitive Advantage: A Ten Year Retrospective on the Resource-Based View. *Journal of Management*, 27, 643-650. <https://doi.org/10.1177/014920630102700602>
- Bell, M., & Pavitt, K., (1995). The development of technological capabilities. Trade, Technology and International Competitiveness. *Economic Development Institute of the World Bank* 69-100
- Bharadwaj, A., S. (2000). A resource-based perspective on information technology capability and firm performance: an empirical investigation, *MIS quarterly*, 169-196.
- Bucher, P., Birkenmeier, B., Brodbeck, H. & Ecscher, J.P., (2003), "Management Principles for Evaluating and Introducing Disruptive Technologies: The Case of Nanotechnology in Switzerland", *R&D Management* 33(2), 149-163.
- Chang, T. & Chuang, S. (2016). Performance implications of knowledge management processes: Examining the roles of infrastructure capability and business strategy. *Expert Systems with Applications* 38, 6170-78
- Cochran, W., G. (1977). *Sampling Techniques*. (3rd ed.). New York: John Wiley & Sons
- Ezuma, K. E., Hamzah, S. R., Ismail, I. A., & Abdullah, A. L. K. (2019). Technology Usage and Organizational Performance in the Medium Sized Manufacturing Enterprises: Does Network Competence Matter. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 9(10), 336-355. <http://dx.doi.org/10.6007/IJARBS/v9->

[i10/6509](#)

- Gholami, R., Sulaiman, A., B., Ramayah, T., & Molla, A. (2013). Senior Manager Perception on Green Information Systems (IS) Adoption and Environmental Performance: Result from Field Survey. *Information and Management*, 50(7), 431-438.
- Gonçalves, L., & de Almeida, F. (2019). How Technology Intelligence is Applied In Different Contexts? *International Journal of Innovation*, 7(1), 104-118. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5585/iji.v7i1.393>
- Hair, J. F., Jr., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., Anderson, R. E., & Tatham, R. L. (2014). Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). An Emerging Toll in Business Research. *European Business Review*, 26(2), 106-121.
- Hair, J. F., Jr., Hult, G., T., M., Ringle, C. & Sarstedt, M. (2016). A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). Sage Publications.
- Hair, J.F., Hult, G.T.M., Ringle, C.M. and Sarstedt, M. (2017), *A primer on Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM)*, Sage, thousand Oaks, CA.
- Halac, D., S. (2015). Multidimensional Construct of Technology Orientation. World Conference on Technology, Innovation and Entrepreneurship. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 195, 1057 – 1065. <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/4.0/>
- Henseler, J. Ringle, C.M. & Sarstedt, M. (2015), A new criterion for assessing discriminant validity in variance-based structural equation modeling, *journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 43(1), 115-135
- Hu, L.-t., & Bentler, P. M. (1998). Fit indices in covariance structure modeling: Sensitivity to underparameterized model misspecification. *Psychological Methods*, 3(4), 424–453. <https://doi.org/10.1037/1082-989X.3.4.424>
- Kabiru J. Ringim, K., J., Razalli, M., R. & Hasnan, N. (2015). The Relationship between Information Technology Capability and Organizational Performance in Nigerian Banks. *International Journal of Technology and Management*, 1(1), 1-10. c. www.sciencetarget.com.
- Kakhki, M., D. & Palvia, P. (2016). Effect of Business Intelligence and Analytics on Business Performance. *Twenty-second Americas Conference on Information Systems, San Diego*. <https://core.ac.uk/display/301368753>
- Karimi, J., Somers, T. M., & Gupta, Y. P. (2001). Impact of Information Technology Management Practices on Customer Service, *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 17(4), 125-158.
- Kihara, P., Bwisa, H. & Kihoro, J. (2016). The Role of Technology in Strategy Implementation and Performance of Manufacturing Small and Medium Firms in Thika, Kenya. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 7(7), 156-167.

- <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/334947483>
- Kihara, P., Bwisa, H. & Kihoro, J. (2016). The Role of Technology in Strategy Implementation and Performance of Manufacturing Small and Medium Firms in Thika, Kenya. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 7(7), 156-167. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/334947483>
- Kilic, A., Cakmak, T., Eren, H. & Sakarya, F. (2016). Technology Intelligence Process In Technopark Firms: An Empirical Research In Turkey. *International Journal Of Economics And Finance Studies*, 8(1), 74-100
- Kumar, U., Kumar, V., & Madanmohan, T. R. (2004). Import-led technological capability: a comparative analysis of Indian and Indonesian manufacturing firms. *Technovation*, 24, 979-993. DOI: 10.1016/S0166-4972(03)00030-0
- Lall, S. (1992). Technological capabilities and industrialization. *World Development*, 20 (2) 165-186
- Leandro. R., G. & Fernando, C., D. A. (2019). How Technology Intelligence Is Applied In Different Contexts? *International Journal of Innovation*, 7(1), 104-122. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.5585/iji.v7i1.393>
- Lee, J. J. and Yoon, H. (2015). A comparative study of technological learning and organizational capability development in complex products systems: distinctive paths of three latecomers in military aircraft industry. *Research Policy*, 44(7), 1296-1313.
- Lichtenthaler, E. (2005). The Choice of Technology Intelligence Methods in Multinationals: Towards A Contingency Approach. *International Journal of Technology Management*, 32(3/4), 388-407.
- Lichtenthaler, E., (2004). Coordination of Technology Intelligence Process: A Study in Technology Intensive Multinationals. *Technology Analysis and Strategic Management*, 16, 197-221.
- Majidfar F. & Salami R., (2011), surveying the role and impact of technology intelligence cycle in enterprises network at research centers and universities, Fourth National Conference on Management of Technology, Iran. Available at www.iramot.ir.
- Mallinguh, E., Wasike, C. & Zoltan, Z. (2020). Technology Acquisition and SMEs Performance, the Role of Innovation, Export and the Perception of Owner-Managers. *Journal of Risk and Fraud Management*, 13 (258), 1-19. doi:10.3390/jrfm13110258
- Manzini, R. & Nasullaev, A. (2017). Technology intelligence in practice A systematic literature review of empirical studies and agenda for further Research. Università Cattaneo Working Papers 2, 1-26.
- Matin, E. K., & Sabagh, P. (2015). Effects of knowledge management capabilities on organisational performance in Iranian export companies. *Mediterranean Journal of*

- Social Sciences*, 6(2), 240–250.
- Mithas, S., Tafti, A., & Mitchell, W. (2013). How a firm's competitive environment and digital strategic posture influence digital business strategy. *MIS Quarterly*, 37(2), 511-536.
- Mochoge, C., Nyakoni, M. & Chepkemoi, P. (2020). Effect of Technological Capability on Performance of Commercial Banks in Kenya. Proceedings of the Kabarak University International Conference on Computing and Information Systems. 7th–10th October.
- Ogunyomi & Bruning, N. (2015). The International Journal of Human Resource Human resource management and organizational performance of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria, (September). <http://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2015.1033640>
- Pena, P., H. (2009). *The SIM Card: An Exercise of Technology Watch Chasing State of the Art and New Opportunities*. (Master's Thesis: Universitat Oberta de Catalunya, Barcelona, Spain)
- Ranjbar, M. S., & Cho, N. (2016). Exploiting technology intelligence in designing and manufacturing complex product systems. *Asian Journal of Information and Communications*, 8(2), 55-68.
- Samat, M. F., Yusoff, M. N. H., Ismail, M., Annual, N., & Mamat, M. (2017). Technological Factor and Social Media Marketing Adoption among SMEs in Kelantan.
- Santos, M., & Corriea, A. (2010). Competitive intelligence as a source of competitive advantage: an exploratory study of the Portuguese biotechnology industry. *Proceedings of the European Conference on Knowledge Management: 867–879*
- Stoel, M., D., & Muhanna, W., A. (2009). IT capabilities and firm performance: A contingency analysis of the role of industry and IT capability type, *Information & Management*, 46(3), 181-189.
- Teece, D., J., Pisano, G. & Shuen, A. (1997). Dynamic Capabilities and Strategic Management. *Strategic Management Journal*, 18, 509-533. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1097-0266\(199708\)18:7<509::AID-SMJ882>3.0.CO;2-Z](http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1097-0266(199708)18:7<509::AID-SMJ882>3.0.CO;2-Z).
- Trez, J., Steffanello, M., Reichert, F., DeRossi, G., & Pufal, N. (2012). Footwear Industry Innovation Capability: Southern Brazilian Evidence: *Academy of Management Meeting, Boston*. 1-32.
- Veugelers, M., Bury, J. and Viaene, S. (2010), "Linking Technology Intelligence to Open Innovation", *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 77, 335-343.
- Wade, M., and Hulland, J. 2004. "Review: The resource-based view and information systems research: Review, extension, and suggestions for future research," *MIS Quarterly*, 28(1), 107-142.

- Yıldız, S., and Karakaş, A. (2012). Defining Methods and Criteria for Measuring Business Performance: A Comparative Research Between the Literature in Turkey and Foreign," *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 10(12), 1091-1102.
- Zawislak, P., A., Alves, A. C., Tello-Gamarra, J., Barbieux, D., & Reichert, F. M. (2012). Innovation capability: From technology development to transaction capability. *Journal of Technology Management and Innovation*. 7 (2) 14-27
- Zollo, M. and Winter, S.G. (2002) Deliberate Learning and the Evolution of Dynamic Capabilities. *Organization Science*, 13, 339 - 351.
<https://doi.org/10.1287/orsc.13.3.339.2780>